

Original Research Article

Ameliorating Effect of some Antioxidants on Haematological Indices in Chlorpyrifos Toxicity Induced Albino Wistar Rats

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Abstract

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The study was aimed at evaluating the ameliorating effect of some antioxidants (garlic, vitamin E, iron, selenium and zinc) on haematological indices in chlorpyrifos toxicity induced albino Wistar Rats. Thirty five (35) adult albino Wistar rats weighing between 180-200g were divided into seven groups of five rats each. Group 1 served as control while 1.86mg/kg of chlorpyrifos (CPF) was administered to group 2. Groups 3-7 were given the same doses of CPF but plus antioxidants i.e. group 3, CPF plus garlic; group 4, CPF plus Vitamin E; group 5, CPF plus Iron; group 6, CPF plus selenium and group 7, CPF plus zinc. The study was conducted over a three weeks period. The results showed significant alteration in haematological indices occasioning the administration of chlorpyrifos. CPF caused a decrease in Hb, PCV, RBC, and platelets and increase in WBC and basophil. Reduction in lymphocyte, neutrophil, monocyte and eosinophil were also observed. Co-administration of the antioxidants offered protection and/or reversal of the effects of the CPF on these haematological indices in the albino Wistar rats. It can thus be concluded that co-administration of these vitamins, minerals and plant with antioxidant activity will protect against CPF induced haematological changes.

Keywords: Antioxidants, Chlorpyrifos, Haematological indices, Toxicity

INTRODUCTION

A Pesticide is defined as any chemical substance used for killing pests which are harmful to animals and plants. Pesticides have various functions which include crop protection, food and plant product preservation, material preservation and disease control (National Resource Council, 1993, USEPA, 2018). Pesticide can also be used as a drying and an antimicrobial agent to prevent fruit from falling off prematurely and as growth regulators (FAO, 2002). In agriculture, these pesticides may be used during production, processing, storage, transport or marketing farm products, wood and wood products or animal feedstuffs (FAO, 2002).

Chlorpyrifos (IUPAC name: *O,O*-diethyl-*O*-[3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinyl]phosphorothionate) (CAS No. 2921-89-2) is a chlorinated organophosphate pesticides with broad spectrum activity (Rosenfeld and Feng, 2011; Hodgson, 2012). It was developed by Dow in 1962,

commercialized in 1965 (Hayes and Laws, 1990; Rosenfeld and Feng, 2011) and registered for public use in the United States when the cumulative risk assessment was completed by the United States Environmental Protection Agency (RED, 2006). It is widely used in agriculture in about 100 countries to control insects and is annually applied to approximately 8.5 million crop acres (Dow chemical company, 2014). Chlorpyrifos is effective in controlling insects such as cutworms, corn rootworms, cockroaches, grubs, flea beetles, flies, termites, fire ants, and lice (US EPA, 1986) and it is being used directly on grains, cotton, field fruits, nuts, vegetable crops and ornamental plants (Vogel, 2016). It is also used for antimicrobial treatment of animal houses, domestic dwellings and farm buildings (King-smith, 1984).

Chlorpyrifos has been reported to be moderately toxic

to humans and chronic exposure to it has been linked to neurological, developmental, and autoimmune disorders (USEPA, 1989; Thrasher *et al.*, 1993; Timofeeva and Levin, 2010; WHO, 2010; Flaskos, 2012; Rauh *et al.*, 2012). Apart from its environmental exposure whereby the insecticide is inhaled in the air, it may bio-accumulate and be consumed by man through the intakes of the food crops that it was used on and it is also readily absorbed through the skin (Hayes and Laws, 1990; USEPA, 2015). Inhalation of chlorpyrifos may cause absorption of the insecticide through the mucous membranes, resulting in systemic intoxication (OHS, 1986) with its severity been dependent on the doses.

Primarily chlorpyrifos, and other organophosphate pesticides, exert their toxicity by interfering with signalling from the neurotransmitter acetylcholine (Christensen *et al.*, 2009; Flaskos, 2012). One chlorpyrifos metabolite, chlorpyrifos-oxon, is an irreversible inhibitor of acetylcholinesterase, preventing this enzyme from deactivating acetylcholine in the synapse leading to a build-up of acetylcholine between neurons and a stronger, longer-lasting signal to the next neuron (Christensen *et al.*, 2009; Flaskos, 2012; Hodgson, 2012). Chlorpyrifos affects the nervous system of humans, pets, and other animals the same way it affects the target pest. Chlorpyrifos is also known to have other, noncholinergic effects. These include inhibition, in humans, of the oxidative metabolism of both testosterone and estradiol (Hodgson, 2012), alteration of serotonin signalling and expression or activity of several serine hydrolase enzymes, including neuropathy target esterase and several endocannabinoid enzymes; it also affects components of the cyclic AMP system and influence other chemical pathways (Slotkin, 2004; Casida *et al.*, 2008; Connors *et al.*, 2008; Eaton *et al.*, 2008). Chlorpyrifos has also been shown to affect haematological indices (Ambali *et al.*, 2010a, 2011; Uchendu *et al.*, 2011) and to also induce oxidative stress in different parts of the brain and liver through increased levels of reactive oxygen species (Mehta *et al.*, 2009; Uchendu *et al.*, 2012).

There is thus a need to identify agents that can mitigated the adverse health consequence of short and long-term exposure to the pesticide. This work is intended to ascertain if co-administration of some antioxidants with Chlorpyrifos will prevent the CPF-induced haematological toxicity in mammals.

In this study three types of antioxidants were used namely metal (Iron, selenium, Zinc), Vitamin (Vitamin E) and plant (garlic).

Iron is an essential nutrient for the growth, development, and long-term survival of most organisms. Most body iron is found as heme iron the essential constituent for oxygen transport in hemoglobin, oxygen storage in myoglobin, and electron transport for cytochrome function in aerobic respiration, and it is even

necessary for signal transduction as a cofactor for nitric oxide synthase and guanylyl cyclase (Wessling-Resnick, 2014). Oral iron supplementation has been recommended for the recovery of the impaired antioxidant defense system in iron deficiency anemia (Kurtoglu *et al.*, 2003).

The ability of zinc to retard oxidative processes has long been recognized. It is thought to exert its antioxidant effect through protection of protein sulfhydryls or reduction of $\cdot\text{OH}$ formation from H_2O_2 through the antagonism of redox-active transition metals, such as iron and copper (acute effect) or induction of some other substance that is the ultimate antioxidant, such as the metallothioneins (chronic effect) (Powell, 2000).

Selenium (Se) is an essential trace element and has attracted tremendous interest because of its important role in antioxidant selenoproteins for protection against oxidative stress initiated by excess reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reactive nitrogen species (NOS) (Tinggi, 2008).

Vitamin E is the collective name for a set of eight related tocopherols and tocotrienols, which are fat-soluble vitamins with antioxidant properties (Herrera and Barbas, 2001; Packer *et al.*, 2001). It is α -tocopherol that is preferentially absorbed and metabolised by the body (Brigelius-Flohé and Traber, 1999).

Garlic (*Allium sativum*) is a species in the onion genus, *Allium* (Block, 2010). It has been used as both a food flavouring and a traditional medicine (National Center for Complementary and Integrative Health, 2012). Garlic is known to contain natural antioxidants that can remove reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reduce lipid peroxides and low-density lipoprotein (LDL) oxidation (Saravanan and Prakash, 2004; Boonpeng *et al.*, 2014; Jang *et al.*, 2018). It is rich in sulfur-containing compounds (Jones and Hughes, 2004), B vitamins (thiamin, Riboflavin, niacin and pantothenic acid, B₆, Folate), Vitamin C, and the dietary minerals manganese, phosphorus, calcium, iron, zinc and selenium (USDA, 2014).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental Animals

Thirty-five (35) adult male albino Wistar rats weighing between 180 and 200g, purchased from a disease free stock of the Department of Biochemistry of the University of Calabar Animal House, were used for the study. The animals were housed in plastic cages with five (5) animals per cage. They were then placed in a well-ventilated animal room at temperature 20-25°C. The animals were allowed two weeks of acclimatization and their weights measured before treatments commenced. Feed (Pfizer Feed Ltd, Lagos, Nigeria) and tap water

were given to the animals *ad-libitum*. Throughout the course of research institutional guidelines for the care and use of laboratory animals were strictly followed.

Treatment of Experimental Animals

Chlorpyrifos EC (48%) was solubilized in a 1:1 mixture of olive oil and water and administered to the experimental animals at 1.86mg/kg body weight. Iron solution was administered at 0.357mg/kg body weight, Zinc at 0.328mg/kg body weight, Garlic at 0.714mg/kg body weight, Vitamin E at 0.419mg/kg body weight and selenium at 1.943mg/kg body weight. The doses used were established from earlier works in our laboratories (Ukpanukpong *et al.*, 2013).

Experimental Design

Thirty five (35) adult albino Wistar rats weighing between 180-200g were divided into seven groups of five rats each. Group 1 served as control while 1.86mg/kg of chlorpyrifos (CPF) was administered to group 2. Groups 3-7 were given the same doses of CPF but plus antioxidants i.e. group 3, CPF plus garlic; group 4, CPF plus Vitamin E; group 5, CPF plus Iron; group 6, CPF plus selenium and group 7, CPF plus zinc. Administration was for three weeks.

Collection of Blood and Haematological Analysis

At the end of the three weeks treatment period all the animals in the groups were subjected to an overnight fast and anaesthetized in chloroform vapour. The animals were sacrificed and whole blood was collected via cardiac puncture using sterile syringe and needle. The whole blood samples were put in ethylene diamine tetra acetate (EDTA) treated samples tubes. The blood samples collected into the EDTA bottles were corked immediately and gently inverted severally to allow the blood mix with the anticoagulant and prevent clotting and cell haemolysis. The haematological analysis were carried out as soon as the blood was collected using Sysmex Hematology Analyzer KX-21N (Whole Blood mode).

Statistical Analysis

The results were analysed for statistical significance by one-way ANOVA using the SPSS statistical program and then with a Post Hoc Test to determine significance between groups using MS excel program. All data were

expressed as Mean \pm SEM and P values <0.05 were considered significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the haematological analysis is shown in Table 1. The results of this study demonstrated a significant alteration in the haematological indices on exposure to chlorpyrifos. CPF caused a decrease in haemoglobin (Hb), packed cell volume (PCV), Red blood cells (RBC), platelets and neutrophils and increase in White blood cells (WBC). The results are in consonance with that of Ghayyur *et al.* (2019) (except that they was increase in platelets count) and Sharma *et al.* (2013). The results of this study also agrees with the work of Savithri *et al.* (2010) who reported decreases in RBC count, Hb, PCV and shrinkage of mean corpuscular volume (MCV), mean corpuscular haemoglobin (MCH) and mean corpuscular haemoglobin concentration (MCHC) of albino rats under CPF toxicity. Studies by Ambali *et al.* (2010a), however, showed an increase in RBC count, Hb, PCV and a decrease in WBC while another study (Girón-Pérez *et al.*, 2006) showed chlorpyrifos not to have any effect on a number of red blood cells, haemoglobin, haematocrit, MCV, MCH, and MCHC. The reverse results by Ambali *et al.* (2010a) was attributed to the mild diarrhoea and the resultant haem concentration. The retarded haemopoiesis in this study may have been due to an induction of DNA damage in hematopoietic tissues namely spleen, bone marrow and lymphocyte as a result of CPF-induced toxicity effects (Sushila *et al.*, 2006) and/or to the effect of the pesticide on blood forming organs (Choudhary and Joshi, 2002). Decreases in Hb and RBC leads to reduction in MCHC. DNA damage in hematopoietic tissues may also be responsible for reductions in monocytes, neutrophils and eosinophils. Neutrophils are involved in phagocytosis during xenobiotic intoxication, during which some neutrophil may rupture releasing free radicals. Neutrophils play essential role in free-radical mediated injury by inducing extracellular release of superoxide and other free radicals (McCord *et al.*, 1994; Uchendu *et al.*, 2012). These free radicals, as well as damaging other hematopoietic tissues, also leads to neutrophil destruction resulting in their decrease in the peripheral circulation (Ambali *et al.*, 2010a). The increase in WBC is a normal physiological response by the defence mechanism of the body following the perception of foreign attack (Guyton and Hall, 1996). There have been other reports of increases of WBC in animals treated with sub lethal doses of insecticide such as lindane and endosulfan (Choudhary and Joshi, 2002). The increase in WBC numbers under chlorpyrifos toxicity in fish was attributed to its activation of the leucopoietic machinery to produce more white blood cells in blood circulation which resulted in

Table 1. Haematological parameters of the various experimental groups

Groups	Hb (g/dL)	PCV (%)	WBC count (x10 ³ /μL)	RBC count (x10 ⁶ /μL)	Platelets (x10 ³ /μL)	MCHC (g/dL)	Lymphocyte (%)	Neutrophil (%)	Monocyte (%)	Eosinophil (%)	Basophil (%)
Control	11.80	35.40	5.06	4.87	380.20	33.28	60.00	24.20	8.60	5.60	0.80
	±0.20	±0.60	±0.21	±0.25	±30.14	±0.04	±2.74	±1.77	±1.29	±1.60	±0.20
Chlopyrifos (p.o)	10.00	33.00	6.08	4.30	350.60	33.22	55.60	20.40	8.00	4.60	1.40
	±0.55*	±1.64*	±0.27	±0.14	±19.37	±0.04	±2.20	±3.11	±1.22	±0.87	±0.24*
Chlopyrifos + Garlic	12.00	36.00	4.98	4.30	401.40	33.46	61.00	29.00	6.40	3.00	1.00
	±0.32 ^a	±0.95 ^a	±0.62	±0.42	±29.17	±0.17	±5.79	±5.57	±0.98	±0.45	±0.32
Chlopyrifos + Vit. E	11.80	35.40	5.22	5.28	378.80	33.16	62.00	23.40	8.20	5.80	1.00
	±0.20 ^a	±0.60 ^a	±0.57	±0.29	±39.33	±0.09	±4.64	±2.75	±1.20	±1.62	±0.00
Chlopyrifos + Iron	12.00	36.00	4.54	5.34	392.60	33.12	63.00	21.20	8.80	5.60	1.40
	±0.32 ^a	±0.95 ^a	±0.25	±0.28 ^b	±33.33	±0.16	±4.06	±2.31 ^a	±1.20	±1.36	±0.24*
Chlopyrifos + Selenium	11.80	35.40	4.16	4.88	368.00	33.34	58.00	28.00	6.80	6.00	1.00
	±0.20 ^a	±0.60 ^a	±0.43	±0.25 ^b	±25.18	±0.17	±2.55	±1.22	±1.11	±1.22	±0.00
Chlopyrifos + Zinc	12.00	36.00	4.38	5.33	379.20	33.46	64.00	21.60	8.00	4.60	1.20
	±0.32 ^a	±0.95 ^a	±0.25	±0.31 ^b	±29.65	±0.16	±4.00	±1.44 ^a	±0.84	±1.12	±0.20

Values are expressed as mean ±SEM, n = 5.

*significantly different from control at p<0.05;

a = significantly different from chlopyrifos at p<0.05;

b = significantly different from chlopyrifos + garlic at p<0.05

increasing the Total Leucocyte Count. Under stress conditions created by toxic substances, the process of lymphopoiesis activated leading to increase in the total number of WBCs (El-Sayed *et al.*, 2007)

The co-administration of antioxidants used in this study (garlic, vitamin E, iron, selenium and zinc) were able to reverse the toxicity effect of the CPF on all the haematological indices it affected. The ameliorative effect of zinc, and vitamin E on chlorpyrifos-induced alteration of haematological parameters in Wistar rats is in agreement with the report of Ambali *et al.* (2010ab, 2011) where the antioxidants were administered prior to exposure to chlorpyrifos. CPF induces oxidative stress in

different parts of the brain and liver through increased levels of reactive oxygen species (Mehta *et al.*, 2009, Uchendu *et al.*, 2012). The administration of these antioxidants may have been responsible for scavenging the CPF induced free radicals in the extracellular medium preventing the onset of radical induced DNA damage and other aberrations in hemopoietic tissues. Furthermore, Vitamin E is an essential intracellular antioxidant in the cytomembranes responsible for the maintenance of cellular integrity (Baker *et al.*, 1996; Ambali *et al.*, 2010a). It is thus probable that membrane stabilization by vitamin E may have played a significant role in the improvement of the cellular integrity of the

neutrophils, preventing the release of the cell damaging free radicals.

CONCLUSION

In summary, the study showed that the antioxidants garlic, vitamin E, iron, selenium and zinc were able to reverse the effect of chlorpyrifos induced toxicity on haematological indices in albino Wistar Rats.

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